

EDITOR'S NOTE AND RESUBMISSION OF D1.1 - ONLINE TECHNOLOGY AND USE CASES OUTLOOK Y1 JUNE 2024

First and foremost, we would like to thank you for your review of the report, which was prepared for deliverable D1.1. We are aware of some shortcomings of this document and the not fully developed vision of the report itself. However, we consider this as a starting point, which allows us and the reviewers to focus on specific aspects and subsequently prepare reports that will be developed each year with the knowledge and experience we acquire during our interaction with SME companies, European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIHs) and other relevant stakeholders. During repeated meetings and discussions on the subject, we have come to some conclusions, which we present in the following sections to better explain the objectives of this report.

Purpose of creating and maintaining the catalogue

The aim of the catalogue is to present solutions available in commercially available products or tested by agrifoodTEF in the context of specific agricultural technologies and use cases that are based on robotics and AI.

In line with the consortium's vision, this document will be largely used internally by the consortium members to modify the scope of their services to meet the needs of the rapidly changing market for newly developed products. However, access to the catalogue will be provided to the public, where, according to our vision, the catalogue's audience will primarily be providers of digital product/services for agri-food farms/companies, which will use it in two ways: they will be able to update it with new technologies, agrifood technologies, functionalities, solutions and use cases, and secondly they will directly benefit from the opportunity to learn about the services that are offered for the solutions in question and will be inspired by learning from examples of others.

Accordingly, there is a need to define the definitions on which to base further considerations. Here, the main concepts are:

Technology outlook in AgrifoodTEF - it refers to forecasts and predictions about future trends and digital solution developments in agriculture. It encompasses both new solutions that are just emerging and existing solutions that are evolving from new use cases of technology mixes or new technologies. Therefore, AgrifoodTEF will use technology outlooks to:

- Identify new opportunities and prepare for change: Understanding upcoming technological changes in solutions can help adapt services and infrastructure to those changes and remain competitive.
- Make informed investments: Technology forecasts can help consortium members make informed investment decisions about new infrastructure, tools, acquisition of new competences to be prepared for testing changing solutions and new use cases.

Technology - a technical solution that makes a given functionality possible (i.e. proximity lidar sensor, GPS, hyperspectral imaging, 5G communication).

Agriculture technology / food processing technology - a method of carrying out a production or process, e.g. autonomous potato harvesting, automatic onion peeling.

Use case / essential use case - publicly observed intention to leverage a new advanced robotics or AI solution to address a specific problem within the agri-food sector. This intention is contextualized by the specific conditions present like i.e. a given location.

Solution - solution in specific product responding to needs in agri-food sector. It may be either a complete system (e.g., an autonomous robot managing phytosanitary product spraying in a vineyard) or a subsystem (e.g., the perception system providing that robot with the capability to decide how

much product to spray), but the key point is that there exists a very specific problem that the solution addresses.

Functionality -it applies to the basic capabilities of a robot system that the system leverages to perform complex activities called "tasks".

Cluster - concentrated group of similar agriculture technologies or/and solutions. Within the cluster, experiences will be exchanged, and service components will be created such as, methodology, infrastructure, metrics (i.e. crop-harvesting, weeding).

Content of the report 1Y

The experience we will gain from offering services will have a direct impact on the scope, quality, and quantity of technologies that will be identified, described, and analysed. Due to the lack of provision of services by the consortium (problems described in the response to the Report dated 13 June 2024) and the lack of contact with EDIHs in the first year, we could not base our report on information obtained from the market. Therefore, we decided to base the first report on the consortium's collective knowledge of available or developing solutions and to focus on the technologies that are available and used in the largest number of products, so to obtain a general picture of the application of new technologies in the agri-food sector. In the following years, we will develop this database primarily based on public information on use cases of new technologies or existing technologies in a new functional-environmental context, the services sought around the functionalities and tasks performed by these solutions. In the first year, we therefore focused on:

1. Collecting information from the European market on available robotic or AI solutions in existing products to identify available technologies and their popularity.
2. Identifying the strengths and weaknesses of the identified technologies, which may indicate potential infrastructure and tests needs for validation.
3. Creating a database of use cases that can be implemented using individual technologies to facilitate the preparation of test infrastructure for these scenarios by consortium members.

Multi-Year Plan for the Development of outlook in the agri-food Sector

2Y. edition

The consortium will already have experience from the first successfully implemented services. The awareness of the needs and ways of using individual technologies will be much greater. In addition, a catalogue of available or new solutions in agriculture will be available online both for browsing and for entering new items by all visitors. Detailed work plan with a report for the next year:

1. Research on which technologies are being used in EDIHs for agricultural solutions (surveys),
2. Mapping identified technology data and use cases to specific services provided by the members of the consortium to the market,
3. Obtaining information from our own consortium's experience in providing services - primarily concerning solutions, technologies and tested use cases (using i.e. Service Requests descriptions),
4. Introducing an online catalogue with submission form (for transparency and classified data security it will need to be based only on publicly available information with links to websites),
5. Starting work on clusters that will provide detailed data on the needs within the framework of individual agricultural technologies.

6. We will develop questionnaires to survey potential AgrifoodTEF customers to identify their specific needs in terms of technologies, services and use cases.

3Y. edition

We plan to develop an outlook for new sources of data and knowledge about technologies and use cases. The development of the catalogue will primarily be based on various sources of information about the direction of market development. We plan to:

1. Deepen cooperation with EDIHs to provide services after the early TRL stage offered by the hubs and thus
2. Gain knowledge and vision of the development trends of solutions and technologies by creating the possibility of obtaining the opinions of experts who will be surveyors and other industry organizations
3. In connection with the development of clusters, a source of information obtained by these groups within.
4. Develop a crawler that automatically searches industry portals (locally and globally - provided by the partners) and web sources on the most important social media portals (LinkedIn, facebook, X) and identifies the occurrence of new use cases with assignment to the location - automatically sends a request to the satellite coordinator to refer to this news (new important / known / unimportant, etc.). If important, it is obliged to describe and refer to how TEF responds to the potential testing needs of the solution presented within the use case.

The plan and development of the catalogue in the coming years will be subject to modifications according to the needs expressed by our members and the companies that use the services. There is no doubt that our knowledge and the level of fulfilment will grow as we gain more experience on services and use cases.

Please find our response to the exact suggestions in the report:

<p>The deliverable provides a generic outlook which is focused on each node. It is unclear what the relevant online technology to be used in the project as a whole is.</p>	<p>The report is projected to be updated each year during the project. In the initial phase, AgrifoodTEF used the knowledge and capabilities of the consortia members to create an overview of the solutions commercially used. The input provided was used for further analysis. Due to delays in national funding, many partners did not start the market research for potential needs/solutions, technologies and business analytics was not performed by them neither. In view of the above, the report is a first version on which further work will be carried out also capitalizing on the reviewers' suggestions. The report is not focused on each node or satellite but rather tries to identify all technologies available across the whole European market. Only later equipped with the knowledge from EDIHs and markets we will be able to analyse members preparation to serve in testing with specific solutions or specific local requirements</p>
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<p>1. Clarify technological focus: Revise the deliverable to explicitly identify and elaborate on the key online technologies that the project intends to leverage. This includes detailing how these technologies will be integrated across various nodes and satellites to achieve the project's overarching goals.</p>	<p>The work will be carried out as described above, but the catalogue that was created giving a clear technological grouping of commercially available products along with the technologies used, their mixes and TRLs of the products was extremely necessary to be made. This maps certain solutions used in Agriculture 4.0 that will be leveraged through the services being provided referring to physical services.</p>
<p>2. Enhance analytical depth: Shift the focus from merely cataloguing companies to providing a thorough analysis of the technologies they offer, their readiness levels (TRL), and their applicability to the project's objectives. This should also involve a critical evaluation of how these technologies can bridge current gaps in agrifood technology and contribute to innovation within the sector.</p>	<p>We need to be aware that companies are very discreet in communicating information about the technologies and technical solutions used, hence cataloguing is not a simple process. Information must be obtained from other sources (SMEs, EDIHs).</p> <p>What needs to be emphasised is that the product catalogue allowed us to define the basic underlying/available technologies and use cases. It is therefore a starting basis on which we will build solutions and use cases outlook of commercial or quasi-commercial solutions that will be tested with the offered services.</p> <p>As stated before, in the Y2 outlook we will try to focus more on solutions provided and use cases rather than analysing just technologies itself since all agrifood solutions are based on mixed subsystems that need validation as whole. This does not imply that services focused on subsystems for direct applications will be excluded (i.e. "test the performance of this model of LiDAR sensor when used to detect the presence of obstacles in a field of tall grass"). Hence it may be a good starting point. This is not the long term objective of the outlook. Scouting technologies seems in this matter as something that is not intended to be done by TEFs as they are established to test, and validated solutions already provided by the companies. This activity should be more on the side of EDIH's, which operate at a lower TRL, where technology can be matched to product or specific use case</p>
<p>3. Improve accessibility and utility of the catalogue: Develop an online platform with advanced search functionalities and a technology submission feature, as planned. This platform should not only facilitate easy access to the catalogued information but also enable continuous updating and expansion of the database with the latest technological</p>	<p>As described earlier, we are aware of the lack of online access to the catalogue but operationally we were not ready to do this with partners who realistically started work late due to funding issues and lack of clear vision of its form.</p> <p>The online catalogue will be developed and made available as soon as possible along with a revision of the whole webpage. For the online</p>

<p>innovations.</p>	<p>catalogue it is necessary to create ontology of information and tree of dependencies with ability of submission function be in place. This works has already started and when completed, information will be gathered through clusters and other channels.</p>
<p>4. Incorporate Ethical, Legal, and Societal Aspects (ELSA): As ELSA considerations are crucial for the project's success, ensure these aspects are integrated into the analysis of technologies and use cases. This will help in identifying potential challenges and opportunities for innovation that are aligned with societal values and legal requirements.</p>	<p>ELSA Aspects will be developed in a next phase of the project within the work packages dedicated to tackle this part. At this stage we have started to identify technologies and essential use cases which is not enough to incorporate ELSA yet. We believe that ELSA can be included within the analysis first when we start providing first services. Mapped technologies confronted with ELSA and other regulatory standards will be done to pinpoint threads and challenges.</p>
<p>5. Strengthen the link between technology and market needs: Conduct a more detailed market analysis to align technological solutions with actual needs within the agrifood sector. This includes mapping the customer journey for potential needs and matching the TEF service offerings to these needs, ensuring the project remains responsive to market dynamics and end-user requirements.</p>	<p>Analysing which technology trends will matter and applying them to new solutions is a task beyond TEF's activities, which should focus on testing and validating solutions where technology has already been applied. What we can do is determine whether the infrastructure and technologies operating within the TEF meet the needs of the identified use cases (e.g. for new robotically advanced or AI technologies in the agri-food sector). Within Y2 of the report, such assessment will be introduced for clusters of identified technologies. In subsequent years, the identification will be more focused on specific use cases, of which there are too few at this point for clear indications of the direction of development and technology needs in terms of services and infrastructure provided.</p>

In conclusion, we would like to express our gratitude for your time and dedication to reviewing our report. Your comments and insights have been extremely important to us and have helped us to improve the content of the catalogue and focus on its purpose. We have carefully analysed your suggestions and have addressed them in the appropriate places in the report.

In addition, we have recognized - for a better common understanding - the need to define exactly the most frequently used definitions and keywords, which could potentially be understood differently depending on the reader.

We hope that this letter and the improved report will be useful to better understand our consortium's vision for the catalogue and its potential applications. We would like to emphasize that this catalogue is only the first step towards creating an information base for the sector of advanced technology products for the agricultural and food processing industries. In the future, we plan to

expand its functionality with new tools and services that will facilitate the development of services towards the validation and testing of these new solutions.

Online technology and use cases outlook Y1

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Dissemination Level

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1. AgrifoodTEF Abstract

AgriFoodTEF is a network of test and validation infrastructures in Europe that supports Agri-Food technology companies to do near product development of their AI and Robotics solutions in real-world facilities. The overall aim is to close the gap between excellent research in these fields and actual products that support an efficient and sustainable agriculture, while meeting stringent usability and economic requirements of their end-users. AgriFoodTEF foundations are solidly rooted in existing experimental farms and facilities for AI and Robotics in Agriculture, already operational in various regions highly representative of European Agri-Food production. These have been clustered to build scale and further enhance EU role in guaranteeing world food security with testing and validation facilities that will engage all relevant stakeholders with the best experts in the AI and Robotics technology domains. Furthermore, standards for dataset creation, data sovereignty, algorithm or benchmark interoperability will be based on GAIA-X as the ambassadors of different GAIA-X agri-domains in Europe are part of the proposal. While each TEF-node will promote independent operations with a sustainable business model that will be optimized for the specialties and territorial needs, all TEF-nodes will share common guidelines, standards and support each other with services that can be also offered across the different regions represented by nodes and satellites. The final aim is to help Europe achieve leadership in fostering top quality, technology driven and massive adoption of innovative solutions for Agri-Food, bringing primary production to new levels of efficiency akin to what was achieved by the Green Revolution.

2. Term and shortcuts

Key terms and shortcuts related to the Report:

Technology outlook in AgrifoodTEF - refers to forecasts and predictions about future trends and solution developments in agriculture. It encompasses both new solutions that are just emerging and existing solutions that are evolving from new use cases of technology mixes or new technologies.

Technology - a technical solution that makes a given functionality possible (i.e. proximity lidar sensor, GPS, hyperspectral imaging, 5G communication).

Agriculture technology / food processing technology - a method of carrying out a production or process, e.g. autonomous potato harvesting, automatic onion peeling.

Use case / essential use case - publicly observed intention to leverage a new advanced robotics or AI solution to address a specific problem within the agri-food sector. This intention is contextualized by the specific conditions present like i.e. a given location.

Solution - solution in specific product responding to needs in agri-food sector. It may be either a complete system (e.g. an autonomous robot managing phytosanitary product spraying in a vineyard) or a subsystem (e.g., the perception system providing that robot with the capability to decide how much product to spray), but the key point is that there exists a very specific problem that the solution addresses.

Functionality - it applies to the basic capabilities of a robot system that the system leverages to perform complex activities called "tasks".

Cluster - a concentrated group of similar agriculture technologies or/and solutions. Within the cluster, experiences will be exchanged, and service components will be created such as methodology, infrastructure, metrics (i.e. crop-harvesting, weeding).

Other terms:

AI (Artificial Intelligence) - It is the ability of machines to exhibit human skills, such as reasoning, learning, planning and creativity. It enables technical systems to perceive their environment, deal with what they perceive and solve problems, while they work toward achieving a specific goal.

IoT (Internet of Things) - IoT describes devices with sensors, processing ability, software and other technologies that connect and exchange data with other devices and systems over the Internet or other communications networks.

ICT (Information and Communication Technologies) - ICTs is a broader term for Information Technology (IT), which refers to all communication technologies, including the internet, wireless networks, cell phones, computers, software, middleware, videoconferencing, social networking, and other media applications and services enabling users to access, retrieve, store, transmit, and manipulate information in a digital form.

DIH (Digital Innovation Hub) - DIHs can help ensure that every company, small or large, high-tech or not, can take advantage of digital opportunities. They also provide innovation services, such as financing advice, training and skills development that are needed for a successful digital transformation. They are a type of one-stop shop for the given range of services.

EDIH (European Digital Innovation Hubs) - EDIHs are one-stop shops supporting companies and public sector organizations to respond to digital challenges and become more competitive.

AgriTech (agricultural technology) - The whole of technologies used in agriculture; currently understood as technologies in agriculture that provide innovative products that increase the productivity and sustainability of agriculture.

Living Lab, Show Field - A new approach to creating and implementing innovative and implementation of innovative solutions in organizations; its basic premise is participation of end users in the entire process of novelty creation, in the form of show laboratories (Living Lab) or crops (Show Field).

R&D (Research and Development) - is the set of innovative activities undertaken by corporations or governments in developing new services or products and improving existing ones. R&D constitutes the first stage of development of a potential new service or the production process.

SMEs (Small and Medium-sized enterprises) - SMEs represent 99% of all businesses in the EU. SMEs are businesses that have a limited number of employees and a relatively low turnover. The definition of SMEs varies by country, but generally, they are defined as businesses with fewer than 250 employees and an annual turnover of less than €50 million.

Micro-enterprises - Micro-enterprises are the smallest type of SMEs, with fewer than 10 employees and an annual turnover of less than €2 million. They are often run by a single person or a small team and are typically focused on a specific niche market.

Small Enterprises - Small enterprises are slightly larger than micro-enterprises, with between 10 and 50 employees and an annual turnover of less than €10 million. They are often more established than micro-enterprises and may have a broader customer base.

CAP - Common Agricultural Policy.

EU CAP Network - The Network is a forum through which National CAP Networks, organisations, administrations, researchers, entrepreneurs and practitioners can share knowledge and information (e.g. via peer-to-peer learning and good practices) about agriculture and rural policy.

EU - European Union.

EC - European Commission.

European Green Deal - is a package of policy initiatives, which aims to set the EU on the path to a green transition, with the ultimate goal of reaching climate neutrality by 2050. It supports the transformation of the EU into a fair and prosperous society with a modern and competitive economy.

European Innovation Partnership (EIP) - a European initiative that promotes innovation to adapt the agricultural sector to environmental and climate challenges. Innovation partnerships mean that farmers, agricultural advisors, researchers and other stakeholders work together in a project to develop practical innovative solutions that occur in agriculture.

Agricultural European Innovation Partnership (EIP-AGRI) - The agricultural European Innovation Partnership (EIP-AGRI) works to foster competitive and sustainable farming and forestry that 'achieves more and better from less'. It contributes to ensuring a steady supply of food, feed and biomaterials, developing its work in harmony with the essential natural resources on which farming depends.

Decision support - These are interactive computer systems that help decision makers use models and data in solving problems unstructured. These systems support organizational and business decision-making activities.

Mobile application - This is the general name for software that runs on a mobile device mobile device, such as phones and tablets; it allows for faster and simpler implementation of services.

Robotization - It is an interdisciplinary field of research dealing with the creation of robots, as well as controlling and operating them.

Satellite - This is the process of identifying the geographical location of a user or device. This can be done through a number of methods, including IP address tracking, GPS tracking and triangulation.

Big data - These are large, both structured and unstructured datasets from various sources that are processed and analysed to obtain new information. This information can be used to create new products, as well as improving the effectiveness and efficiency of processes, including processing information to enable better insight, decision-making and automation.

Autonomous - These are devices capable of autonomously navigating a designated area, which collect internal and external data, and then respond to them in two ways: they receive and transmit the data to a computer or, equipped with artificial intelligence, for example, react directly - in the field of agriculture, for example, they increase the dosage of fertilizer or adjust the lighting in a room.

Augmented reality - It is a technology based on the integration of digital information and the user's environment in real time. For example, this applies to solutions involving the superimposition of additional information, such as text or graphics, on objects in the user's environment user, which are displayed on the screen of a device such as a smartphone.

Precision farming - is a management approach that focuses on (near real-time) observation, measurement, and responses to variability in crops, fields and animals. It can help increase crop yields and animal performance, reduce costs, including labour costs, and optimise process inputs.

Smart agriculture - Also known as Farming 4.0 or digital farming, smart farming incorporates information and communication technologies into machinery, equipment and sensors used in agricultural production systems. Technologies such as the IoT and cloud computing are advancing this development even further by introducing more robots and artificial intelligence into farming.

WoS - Web of Science.

3. Executive summary D1.1 Online technology and use cases outlook Y1 (2023)

This report provides an overview of technologies in the field of agrifoodTEF project currently used in agriculture, analysing their potential development trends based on their advantages, disadvantages, and use cases. It also aims to provide an outlook on how these technologies may evolve in the future, considering past changes and advancements. The report is structured by functionality and outlines the agricultural technologies that can be implemented using these technologies. It is complemented by a list of commercially available devices that AgrifoodTEF network has identified as utilizing the respective technology. A critical component of the analysis is to present potential services and their extent, mindful of the shortcomings of the utilized technological components.

4. Method used

The report is the first attempt to analyse the technologies and use cases that consortium members have encountered and are working with. Information for this report was collected in December 2023 through questionnaires and a form that was completed by active members. As an additional source of information, the authors used information available on individual manufacturers' websites and online catalogues compiling agriculture of the future or simply agriculture 4.0.

This catalogue includes detailed information about various types of technology, including mobile robots, UAVs, autonomous kits, and specialized tools for tasks such as weeding, tillage, seeding, fertilizing, irrigation, harvest, and livestock management. By technology, we mean the equipment and its systems for operating control, monitoring, collecting and processing data collected in various ways, which together serve to carry out the activities resulting from the assumptions that determine their functionality. Each section elaborates on the specific technologies, their functionalities, use cases, and the technical solutions they employ. Additionally, it highlights the pros and cons of technology, trends regarding technology, and potential services and scope that could leverage these technologies. A graphical diagram of the layout of the catalogue is included in Fig.1 to help understand the idea behind its construction and also to help analyse its compactness.

Figure 1. Layout diagram of the catalogue

5. Technology development catalogue

The following catalogue details technologies related to AI, data and robotic technologies in the agriculture and food sector. As an overarching criterion, a breakdown into functionalities defining the scope and capabilities of the devices and their components has been adopted. For each of the 4 indicated functionalities, the broad commercial ranges of currently used devices equipped with devices, technological systems that allow them to work within the functionality to which they have been assigned are included. The catalogue also contains descriptions of the main advantages and disadvantages, as well as the possibilities and direction of development of devices, systems included in each functionality.

5.1. Functionality: Positioning (guidance) the unit implementing technologies used in agriculture

Positioning (guidance) of an agricultural unit (machine + tractor) or autonomous device (tractor, implement carrier, machine) equipped with an agricultural machine suitable for the implementation of agricultural technology.

Agricultural technology it applies:

Sowing, planting, mechanical weed control, chemical weed control, field and crop cultivation, crop harvesting,

General scope of use cases:

- Control and determination of the route for an agricultural unit or autonomous device, including straight driving, obstacle avoidance, and turns along the optimal and shortest trajectory in order to achieve maximum efficiency and quality of work of the device and machines.
- Obstacle detection.
- Positioning of machinery and equipment working in field crops: sowing, mechanical and chemical crop protection, fertilization and crop harvesting.
- Positioning of areas with diseased, weakened, heavily weedy plants requiring intervention for other reasons as well.

1. RTK GPS (Real-Time Kinematic GPS)

RTK GPS is a high-tech positioning system that corrects errors in regular GPS, giving incredibly accurate location data in real-time. It works by using a network of fixed stations that send correction signals to the receiver. This can provide accuracy down to centimetres, making it ideal for tasks like surveying and precision agricultural.

Example of the use of commercial solutions:

- Mobile robots (tool carriers):

- FarmDroid FD20 (Farmsystems): Fully automatic, solar powered field robot that automates your seeding and plant protection. Use high-precision GPS technology. Used to accurately determine the position of each plant.
- Dino (Naïo Technologies): Initial purpose of the Dino is weeding. However, due to its power and accurate driving in practice it's also already putted in action on farms for sowing and (small) tillage jobs. The robot uses GPS RTK for navigation.
- Orio (Naïo Technologies): Autonomous tool carrier for vegetables and industrial crops. Orio work in fields with accuracy thanks to its guidance system based on RTK GPS signal.
- Oz (Naïo Technologies): Oz works completely autonomously thanks to its RTK GPS guidance system.

- Ted (Naio Technologies): Autonomous tool carrier for vineyards. Guidance based on RTK GPS signal. Used for mechanical weeding under the row.
- Bakus (Vitibot): Bakus is a viticultural straddle robot that integrates a wide range of modular tools for efficient work in vineyards. The robot uses RTK GPS technology for its movements.
- Zilus (SABI AGRÍ): Zilus is an all-terrain robot its height and width can be adapted to meet every need. Its modular design means it can be adapted to all crops. The robot is equipped with a centimetre-level RTK GPS to ensure precision.
- ICS20HD-plug-in hybrid, ICS20E - electric (AutoAgri): Is a multifaceted implement carrier, available in fully electric and plug-in hybrid variants, engineered for eco-friendly and precise farming operations. Primary navigation by GPS with RTK.
- haRiBOT (HariTech): The robot can drill holes fully automatic for new plantations. The robot is a universal machine, can also put many other implements, like sprayer, fertilizer, cultivator etc. Navigation and control RTK GPS.
- Dot Power Platform (Raven Technologies): The platform drives itself and any attached implement, such as a seeder or sprayer, through a combination of GPS technology and associated precision computer systems.
- OMNIPOWER 3200 (Raven Technologies): The powered-up autonomous power platform's attaches to interchangeable implements, such as a seeder, spreader, and sprayer. The robot uses RTK GPS for staying within geofenced field boundary.

- UAV:

- L30 Spraying Drone (ABZ innovation): Drone equipped with an advanced flight planning algorithm and optimized downward airflow, offers unparalleled performance in drone technology, providing precision and efficiency in a wide range of applications. Use an advanced RTK system.
- Koliber VTOL (BZB UAS): Drone with precision cameras and GPS modules, it is able to inspect individual plants.
- HF T72 (Hongfei Aviation Technology Co): The HF T72 is a super large capacity agricultural drone, It can spray 28-30 hectares of fields per hour with very high efficiency, uses smart batteries, and charges quickly. Perfect for large areas of farmland or fruit forests. The drone use GPS positioning function, autonomous flight function, terrain following function.

- Autonomous kits:

Tools: Fertilizing

- LeapCat (BBLeap): Multi-level prescription maps for extreme precision. GPS signals determine the exact location of the sprayer. LeapCat adds the exact location of the booms and nozzles to it.

Other: Tools & Data

- agroOSA: Automatic control systems for agricultural vehicles with modern solutions based on RTK.

Pros of technology:

- **High precision:** RTK GPS provides centimeter-level accuracy, which is essential for precision field work such as seeding, spot-spraying, weeding and fertilizing. Enables the preservation of the established optimum amount of seed sown during punctual seeding as a result of maintaining uniformity in the spacing of seeded rows and the distribution of plants in the row, switching off seeding sections to avoid double seeding, for example. Allows

the use of non-chemical methods of destroying weeds in between rows and between plants in the row. Allows precise application of fertilizers at the seed or germinating plant in the row, thus reducing the global amount of fertilizers (chemical elements) applied on the surface of a given field reducing the economic and environmental costs of mineral and organic fertilization processes.

- **Weather independence:** RTK GPS works regardless of weather conditions.

Cons of technology:

- **Cost:** RTK GPS systems are expensive both in installation and maintenance.
- **Dependence on Satellite signal:** It requires a stable GPS signal, which can be problematic in areas with high forestation or in deep valleys. (Investment in infrastructure near the application can also cause an increase in costs.)

Trends regarding technology:

- **Cost reduction:** Innovations are aimed at reducing the costs of components and implementation. Work is underway to increase the availability of RTK signals in regions with difficult terrain configurations, including terrain obstacles such as high dense trees, ground technical installations.
- **Developments of different satellite systems.** Actions to expand the offer by being able to adapt data from different dispatch systems, both public and commercial.

Potential agrifoodTEF services and scope:

- **Positioning accuracy:** Measurement of positioning deviation in various field conditions (e.g., in an open field, near obstacles).
- **Signal stability:** Tests of GPS signal stability under various atmospheric and terrain conditions.
- **Integration with Robotic, Autonomous, Automatic Systems:** Testing RTK GPS integration with real-time agricultural robots, evaluating the effectiveness of automating operations such as seeding or fertilizing.
- Comparison with geodetic reference data.
- Evaluation of the repeatability of positioning results.
- Resistance to disturbances and integration of other, backup positioning sources.

2. GNSS (Global Navigation Satellite System)

GNSS is a system designed to determine the exact position of a point or moving object in three dimensions based on the measurement by the receiver of the radio signal's travel time from the satellite to the receiver's antenna. In order to determine the coordinates, it is necessary to process signals from at least four satellites and to know their position during the measurement.

Examples of the use in commercial solutions:

- Mobile robots (tool carriers):

- Slopehelper (PeK Automotive): To navigate on a plantation the robot uses differential GNSS, touch sensors, and radars.
- Robotti (Agrointelli): Robotti is an autonomous implement carrier highly suited for precise and accurate plant establishment and plant nursing tasks in row and bed crops for both arable and horticultural production. The robot uses RTK-GNSS positioning system.
- Jo (Naïo Technologies): The robot uses RTK-GNSS guidance system to navigate between rows of vineyards.
- Tipard 350 (Digital Workbench): Primarily navigates with two RTK-GNSS receivers in combination with an IMU.
- Tipard 1800 (Digital Workbench): The Robot works with a dual RTK-GNSS receiver.

- **YT5113A Robot Tractor (Yanmar):** The system is based on RTK-GNSS which can utilise signals from multiple global navigation satellite systems (GNSS) and the base station.
- **Ceol (Agreenculture):** The robot uses GNSS RTK for navigation and geo-positioning. The field robot is an inter-row crawler. It can work several hectares per day fully autonomous and its rear tool carrier allows it to tow different tools.

Pros of technology:

- **Wide range of applications:** The ability to use anywhere and anytime: GNSS provides a positioning signal from satellites anywhere to determine the position of its user. This allows for navigating autonomous or automatic vehicles on the surfaces of all kinds of plantations or crops.
- **Flexibility:** Weather Independence: GNSS operates independently of weather conditions.
- Low cost of purchasing a basic set, receiver.

Cons of technology:

- **Accuracy:** Lower precision: achieving large, centimetre accuracy requires the use of touch receivers and the system to make computational corrections based on time data and an additional antenna (base station) on the surface of the crop, plantation.
- **Interference:** Satellite signal dependence: Requires a stable GPS signal, which can be problematic in areas with high forestation or in deep valleys.
- Possibility of occurrence of intentional interference with the system, e.g. by the military.

Trends regarding technology:

- Cost reduction: Innovations are aimed at reducing the costs of components and implementation.
- **Integration with other systems:** Combining GNSS with RTK technologies and vision sensors to increase precision.
- Software development: Improvement of correction algorithms and signal filtering to increase accuracy.
- Work on increasing the availability of GNSS signals: In regions with difficult terrain configurations, including terrain obstacles such as high dense trees, ground technical installations.

Potential agrifoodTEF services and scope:

- **Positioning accuracy:** Measurement of positioning deviation in various field conditions (e.g., in an open field, near obstacles).
- **Signal stability:** Tests of GPS signal stability under various atmospheric and terrain conditions.
- **Integration with Robotic systems:** Checking the integration of GNSS with agricultural robots in real time, assessing the efficiency of automation operations such as sowing or fertilizing.
- Comparison with reference geodetic data.
- Evaluation of the repeatability of positioning results.
- Resistance to interference and integration of other, backup positioning sources.

Tests:

1. **Initialization time:** Measurement of the accuracy of GNSS positioning in different locations and conditions (e.g. forest cover, valleys).
2. **Multisystems:** Testing the operation of different satellite constellations (GPS, GLONASS, Galileo) and their impact on accuracy.
3. **Initialization time:** Measurement of the time it takes to obtain a stable signal after the system has started up.

Validation:

- Field tests using fixed control points.
- Analysis of positioning accuracy compared to industry standards.

3. Simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM)

SLAM is an advanced technique used in robotics and autonomous systems. Its purpose is to allow robots or other mobile devices to simultaneously create a map of an unfamiliar environment and determine their position in that map. It is a technology based on a laser scanner and software that allows it to map its environment while positioning itself in that environment. It is thanks to SLAM that robots can effectively navigate dynamic and often unfamiliar spaces.

Examples of the use in commercial solutions:

- Mobile robots (tool carriers):

- AGV - Automated Guided Vehicle (Atria) is an autonomous vehicle that is used in a variety of industrial processes to move goods before, during or after the manufacturing process, or perform other types of functions such as planting in a field. These vehicles are usually introduced into controlled environments and use sensors such as lasers or cameras to avoid obstacles, such as the workers in the factory itself. There are also AGVs that work by wire-guided
- Bonirob (Amazone) - agribot uses video- and laser-based positioning as well as satellite navigation to find its way around the fields and with cameras and computer-based image analysis, it recognizes and classifies plants (Bosch Deepfield Robotics).
- Mamut (Cambridge Consultants): Is an AI-powered autonomous robotic platform. Equipped with an array of sensors, Mamut maps and navigates its surroundings without the need for GPS or fixed radio infrastructure. As it travels the rows of a field, orchard or vineyard, cameras capture detailed crop data at the plant level, enabling accurate predictions of yield and crop health. It integrates stereo cameras, LIDAR, an inertial measurement unit (IMU), a compass, wheel odometers and an on-board AI system that fuses the multiple sensor data inputs. This sophisticated blend of technologies enables vehicle to know where it is and how to navigate through a new environment, in real time.
- TerraSentia (EarthSense): Robot is a vehicle equipped with multiple cameras and LIDAR sensors that runs around the farmland (level 2 automatic driving), which is important for the width of the stem of the target crop / plant, leaf area index, leaf and stem disease. It is a system that can collect plant characteristic data and measure it with high accuracy. The acquired field data is seamlessly transformed into quantitative and consistent information by machine learning-based analysis.
- Dood (EarthAutomations): autonomous robots for agriculture can be paired up with different existing implements to perform farm work 24/7, depending on which implement is attached. Thanks to the 3-point hitch, different equipment can be attached to the back and the robot can be programmed to do field work autonomously. It uses computer vision to navigate, thanks to which it can also detect different pests and diseases on the field. Depending on environment conditions and type of mission, the robot can perform waypoint navigation through RTK-gps or use a pre-built map to autonomously navigate in the field with the aid of cameras and computer vision algorithms like SLAM, AI-based object detection and obstacle avoidance. Using one or more stereo cameras the robot is able to perceive depth and distances.
- La Chèvre (Nexus Robotics): Robot is able to recognise crops at all stages of growth. It uses AI to differentiate between weeds and crops and then pulls out weeds that are very close to the crops without damaging the crops. Multiple RTK-gps sensors provide position and orientation for navigation while the robot is scanning the underlying crops and weeds with cameras and depth sensors. With calibration methods, the camera and depth sensor measurements are fused by using

SLAM methods. SLAM (Simultaneous Localisation and Mapping) let's build a map and localise a vehicle in that map at the same time enabling vehicles to map out unknown environments. This local map holds the coordinates of the plants.

Pros of technology:

- **Wide range of applications:** Can be used anywhere, anytime: SLAM allows navigation in unfamiliar environments without the need for prior terrain mapping. This makes it possible to navigate autonomous or automated vehicles on the surfaces of any type of plantation or crop.
- **Flexibility:** Can work in unknown environments without pre-loading of terrain data
- **Adapting to change:** The multisystem nature of navigation data collection and processing allows the equipment to react dynamically to changing environmental conditions.
- **Wide working conditions:** allows mapping in restricted areas not covered by GPS navigation.

Cons of technology:

- **High computing power of the system:** Correct operation of the system in real time requires very high computing power and correct overlapping of point clouds generated from information acquired from cameras and sensors.
- **Cost of equipment:** achieving the right image depth requires the use of a multi-camera system and considerable computing power, which affects the cost of the entire control system.
- **Inaccuracy of the position of the autonomous device:** in the absence of the possibility to determine the absolute position of the device in the field, its localisation error remains variable, as it is based on the last known position and orientation of the robot. Therefore, in such a case, it is necessary to both determine the position on the map and create a new map fragment for the new terrain.
- The possibility of deliberate interference with the system, e.g. by the military.

Trends regarding technology:

- **Cost reduction:** Innovation is moving towards lower component and implementation costs.
- **Software development:** Improving signal correction and filtering algorithms to increase accuracy.

Potential agrifoodTEF services and scope:

- **Positioning accuracy:** Measurement of positioning deviation under different field conditions (e.g. open field, near obstacles).
- **Signal stability:** Stability tests of sensor and camera signals under different weather and field conditions.
- **Integration with robotic, autonomous systems:** Verification of the integration of the SLAM system with agricultural robots in real time, evaluating the effectiveness of automation of operations such as sowing or fertilization.
- Comparison with geodetic reference data.
- Immunity from interference and integration of other, backup positioning sources

Tests:

1. **Accuracy and range:** Measurement of positioning accuracy with the SLAM system in different locations and conditions (e.g. woodland, valleys).
2. **Initialisation time:** Measurement of the time it takes to obtain a stable signal and accurate positioning of the device, depending on the available number of cameras, sensors and computing power once the system is up and running.
3. **Compatibility of the control equipment making up the system:** Interoperability tests of the object position control, terrain and obstacle recognition and terrain mapping devices that make up SLAM-type systems.

Validation:

- Field tests using fixed control points.
- Analysis of positioning accuracy compared to accepted standards.
- Analysis of the correctness of autonomous vehicle guidance.

4. Multisystem positioning (mix of different positioning and localization technologies)**e.g. RTK-GPS + RTK-GNSS**

Multisystem positioning is the combination of the functionality of two or more different positioning systems, e.g. RTK+GPS, to achieve high real-time accuracy. The RTK system determines corrections to the GPS system to compensate for positioning errors.

Examples of the use in commercial solutions:

- Mobile robots (tool carriers):

- Automato Robotics Sunjer A2 (Directed Machines): The robot has highly precise RTK-gps/GNSS for navigation.
- Land-A2 (Exobotic Technologies): Navigation system with dual antenna RTK-gps, LiDAR sensors to detect obstacles in the vicinity of the robot.
- Traxx (Exxact Robotics): Is a robot specialised for narrow vines with navigation system with RTK-gps and LiDAR sensors to detect obstacles. It offers a variety of use (tillage and spraying).
- Oxin (Smart Machine): Is a fully autonomous multitasking robot for safe, efficient, and sustainable vineyards and orchards. The robots drive pre-planned missions using LiDAR and camera for real time driving adjustments and implement positioning and control. Mission and block information is logged by customers using RTK-gps logging devices to create base line drive paths and identify in orchard hazards and block boundaries.
- Swarmbot 5 (SwarmFarm): Robot platform for horticulture, orchard and large-scale agriculture applications. Navigation system with 2cm RTK GPS with IMU and wheel odometry. Obstacle detection 3D Lidar and 3D time of flight infrared cameras.
- Herbicide GUSS (Guss): Robot developed for spraying fruit trees. GUSS uses a sophisticated combination of GPS, LiDAR, vehicle sensors.
- mini GUSS (Guss): Uses a combination of GPS, LiDAR, cameras and the latest technology to autonomously roll through the orchards, day or night spraying row after row.
- Trektor (Sitia): Robot is guided by GNSS and RTK navigation.
- Robot One - V2023 (Pixelfarming Robotics): Navigation system with dual RTK-gps and camera sensing.
- Agbot 5.115T2 (AgXeed): The robot uses RTK GNSS for precise guidance and safe positioning: $\pm 2,5\text{cm}$ Communications module for bidirectional data transfer and RTK correction.
- Agbot 2.055W3 (AgXeed): The robot uses RTK GNSS for precise guidance and safe positioning: $\pm 2,5\text{cm}$ Communications module for bidirectional data transfer and RTK correction. Can be used for crop protection, weed control, the application of liquid nutrition and for mowing and shredding prunings.
- Agbot 2.055W4 (AgXeed): The robot uses RTK GNSS for precise guidance and safe positioning: $\pm 2,5\text{cm}$ Communications module for bidirectional data transfer and RTK correction.
- Agbot 5.115T2 (AgXeed): The robot uses RTK GNSS for precise guidance and safe positioning: $\pm 2,5\text{cm}$ Communications module for bidirectional data transfer and RTK correction.

- **Autonomous kits:**

Tools: Smart Weeders

- **Welaser (Pixelfarming Robotics):** The robot use the guidance solution with GNSS/RTK positioning.

Pros of technology:

- **Flexibility:** Can be customized and adapted to the specific needs of agricultural applications.
- **Integration:** Ease of integration with other positioning and navigation systems.
- **Precision:** Can offer greater data accuracy as a result of synergy of data from different sources, devices.

Cons of technology:

- **Environment dependence:** Effectiveness can depend on environmental and topographical conditions.
- **Compatibility:** combining data from many different sources, transmitted using different protocols, can lead to errors and positioning inaccuracy in reading the data or inability to read the transmitted data.
- **Cost:** putting together different positioning devices into a single system can lead to increased costs due to, among other things, the need for devices with significantly higher computing power.

Trends regarding technology:

- **Multisensor integration:** Combining different positioning technologies to increase precision and reliability.
- **Algorithm development:** Improving data fusion algorithms and error correction.

Tests:

1. **Accuracy and consistency:** Measurement of positioning accuracy in different environments (e.g., open field, near buildings).
2. **Integration with Infrastructure:** Testing the integration of different positioning and guidance technologies combined into a system, such as GNSS or RTK GPS, Lidar, evaluating the improvement in accuracy of the overall system performance.
3. **Energy Efficiency:** Evaluation of the energy consumption of positioning systems and their impact on the working time of robots
4. **Compatibility:** Compatibility tests, cooperation of systems forming one positioning and guidance system installed on the tested autonomous vehicle.

Validation:

- Comparison with positioning results of other systems.
- Analysis of consistency of results under different operational conditions.
- Analysis of compatibility of systems within the system,

5.2. Functionality: Recognition of objects in space, area mapping

Object recognition and terrain mapping aim to support the functionality of autonomous agricultural units, as well as harvesters and self-propelled agricultural machinery equipped with agricultural devices for the implementation of agricultural technologies, leading to obtaining the required precision, efficiency, quality of work and obtaining measurable environmental (natural, ecological), economic and social benefits. Object recognition systems are also used to assess the location and condition of livestock, the state of cleanliness of livestock buildings, or the control of feed distribution in feed corridors. Recognized objects also include crops, weeds, crops waiting to be harvested: fruit,

vegetables, potato ridges, beet rows or cereal patches. The range of objects recognized in this way also includes any obstacles in the fields and in the driving paths of autonomous machines.

General scope of use cases:

- Positioning of areas with diseased, weakened, heavily weedy plants requiring intervention for other reasons as well.
- Positioning of crop sowing.
- Obstacle detection.
- Positioning of animals and assessment of their physical condition.
- Assessment of the cleanliness of livestock buildings and the status of feed distribution in feed corridors.
- Positioning of feed or excrement areas of concentration for their appropriate assignment to animals or removal from the livestock building.
- Segregation of images and facilities to assess yield levels.

Agricultural technology it applies:

Sowing, planting, mechanical weed control, chemical weed control, field and crop cultivation, crop harvesting, feeding, removal of droppings

1. Vision Sensors

Vision sensors as a combination of different types of sensors (RGB, multispectral, thermal, 2D, 3D, etc). It is an array of cameras and sensors for image and signal capture, information transfer and the software responsible for image processing and analysis.

Examples of the use in commercial solutions:

- Mobile robots (tool carriers):

- Odd.bot (Odd.bot): Fully autonomous weeding. Recognizing weeds using computer vision.
- Andela Robot Weeder (ARW-912) (Andela Techniek & Innovatie): Weed recognition with RGB camera.
- WEAI (Ekobot): Recognizing weeds using an RGB camera.
- Agri Jacobus (AGROCOM POLSKA): Recognize weeds in real time using a vision system in row crops.
- Robotti 150D (Agrointelli): Camera systems allows it to view the crop row. Using an RGB color profile, the technology distinguishes plants from weeds.
- Valera (Ant Robotics): Stereo cameras for navigation and obstacle detection, nearfield sensors for obstacle detection, safety shutoff.
- HammerHead (FieldRobotics): Inside the orchard it uses only data coming from laser scanner and cameras to navigate inside the orchard.
- Prospr (Robotics Plus): Navigation with a combination of vision systems (LiDAR + cameras), for intelligent obstacle detection and avoidance.
- MK-V (Robotics Plus): Use the latest computer vision technology to cultivate the land with greater precision and accuracy.
- Robovator (F. Poulsen Engineering): The robot is equipped with a special plant detection camera above each row of crop.
- RoboWeeder (Smart Farm Robotix): Solar powered weeding robot, use Artificial Intelligence image recognition to spot the weeds among desired plants and utilize smart sensors to provide our robot with self-navigation in and around the field.
- Titan FT-35 (FarmWise): Is an automated mechanical weeder that distinguishes crops from harmful weeds using computer vision. Is adaptable to different crops, soils and growth stages.

It uses cameras and sensors for navigation and removes 95% of all weeds with surgical accuracy while leaving vegetables untouched.

- UAV

UAVs as carriers of sensors, cameras, etc., cooperate within platforms, teams of devices, and teleinformatics systems for positioning and mapping the terrain.

- Demeter EA-20XE (EAVision): The EA-20XE is a plant protection drone with stereo vision perception technology. With sensitive perception and autonomous obstacle avoidance, EA-20XE ensures safe and precise flying without the need to survey plots in complex environments.
- MIDA/EYE-SCAB (Metacortex): MIDA permits to obtain a clear indication about the pathogen infection risk among fruit orchards. The forecast of infection risk is permitted by the innovative combination between weather data and drone aerial imagery. The prediction is then obtained by combining the multi-spectral aerial imagery with wetness index to output a localized risk index. To do this, the APR was equipped with a radiometric thermal imaging camera and a six-band multispectral sensor.
- T630 (Shenzhen Titan Flying Technology Co): The agriculture drone has a 30-litre capacity, high efficiency and can spray 12 hectares per hour. The field of view of the camera is 120°, the resolution is 720P. The drone also has a FPV Spotlight of 900 lumens.
- DJI Agras T50 (DJI Agriculture): The agriculture drone integrates aerial surveying, spraying, and spreading into a single drone. T50 features dual Active Phased Array Radars and binocular vision sensors. These work together to accurately reconstruct the T50's surroundings and detect nearby obstacles, for intelligent obstacle sensing and bypassing, and Terrain Following over slopes.
- Kisan Agri Drone V2 (Garuda): The drone is specifically designed for agricultural applications. The drone is equipped with various sensors, cameras and other technologies that enable it to collect data and perform tasks related to farming and crop management. The drone can assist in precision farming techniques by precisely applying fertilizers, pesticides, or herbicides.

- Autonomous kits (tool carriers):

Tools: Smart Weeders

Smart weeders as carriers of both positioning devices, terrain mapping devices, and executive devices for agricultural technologies applied at a given place and time (agricultural tools).

- Laserweeder (Carbon Robotics): Use lasers with tracking cameras.
- UX Amaspot (Amazone): The technique employs chlorophyll-detecting fluorescence sensors.
- See&Spray select (John Deere): The advanced camera detection and artificial intelligence systems from the See & Spray platform for targeted in-season weed control.
- Robocrop Spot Sprayer (Garford): Uses video image analysis techniques to identify individual plants using a custom colour sensor spectrum thereby identifying weeds from plants.
- I-spray (Kuhn): Fitted with hyperspectral sensors on the boom, the sprayer constantly monitors the vegetation being treated. Artificial intelligence is used to analyse the images and recognise adventive species that need treating.
- WEEDit Ag (Rometron): The WEED-IT detects chlorophyll in actively growing weeds in fallow fields, identifying and targeting them with high accuracy. The Weed-IT cameras were able to identify weeds and send a signal to the nozzles to spray only green plants in brown areas.
- Weed-IT Quadro (Rometron): Camera-controlled precision/spot spraying.

- IMPAACT (Berthoud): The solution detects weeds in real time thanks to cameras set up directly on the sprayer boom. Sensors discriminate crops and weeds species, and only the chosen weeds are sprayed.
- Greeneye (Green Eye Technology): Cameras mounted directly onto spraying machines enabling rapid detection and classification of weeds down to the species level.
- Eco Sniper (Milar): Camera-controlled precision/spot spraying. Eco Sniper has developed a system that detects weeds in real time through optical cameras.
- SprayING (Farm-ING Smart Farm Equipment): The AI-based camera system enables precise differentiation between crops and weeds.
- InRowING (Farm-ING Smart Farm Equipment): The state-of-the-art camera system, which is based on artificial intelligence, detects crops and unwanted weeds in the early stages of growth and combats them automatically.
- iSelect (K.U.L.T.): Weeding system with camera-controlled tool guidance enables precise work between crops in the row.
- Vulcan (FarmWise): Vulcan precision weeding implements the computer vision and AI in the FarmWise Intelligent Plant System (IPS) Scanner. Sophisticated detection models were developed by gathering a vast number of images and annotating them to accurately distinguish between individual crops and weeds. Using these detection models, the system determines the position of crops and the location of every crop stem.

Tools: Tillage

- CoSpectroCam (AgriWatch): Remote Sensing and monitoring services at local and regional scales using the combination of RGB camera and hyperspectral sensor.

Tools: Fertilizing

- ARA (Ecorobotix): Precision spot spraying implement using RGB cameras
- UX 5201 SmartSprayer (Amazone): Image recognition system detects any weeds at a very early growth stage, in order to apply herbicides to the target surface with high precision and efficacy.
- SprAI (DeepAgro): Based on a combination of software, artificial intelligence, RGB cameras, microcomputers and solenoid valves, which allows the detection weeds in different environments and applying the exact dose of product only on the target.
- VR Lettuce Thinner (Vision robotics corporation): Vision-guided precision spraying machine with camera-controlled tool to thin lettuce, based on Deep Learning.
- LeapBox (BBLeap): Spraying based on plant recognition, the camera technology determines the amount of biomass and adjust the dosage based on biomass if desired.

Tools: Livestock management

- JOZ Tech Manure Robots (JOZ Tech): The robot use advanced sensor technology to navigate and clean efficiently, ensuring a high level of hygiene in the barn.
- GEA Srone (GEA Srone): Is an advanced manure removal system designed for dairy farms.
- Hetwin Avenger (Hetwin): is a robot specifically designed for automated manure removal in barns and livestock housing. It uses a combination of sensors and intelligent navigation systems to move around the barn, collecting and disposing of manure.
- Mestrobot RS450 (DeLaval): Scraper robot for slatted floors is equipped with features to help maintain hygiene in the barn.
- Discovery 90 S/SW (Lely): Manure robot. The fecal removal robot cleans the barn floor continuously: 24 hours a day, seven days a week.

- Schauer Enro (Schauer): The robot specializes in manure removal in pig and cattle farms. It automates the cleaning process, using sensor technology to navigate through the barn and efficiently remove manure.
- Vector: Automatic feeding according to the needs of each group of animals is precision feeding.
- Juno (Lely): Robotic feeding. Increasing the frequency of feed pick-up pays off - pick-up encourages cows to take feed frequently throughout the day and night, which increases feed intake.
- Optimat (Delaval): Automatic feeding systems relieve the burden of all routine tasks, while ensuring regular feeding of fresh feed.

Others: Tools & Data

- AiCPlus (Agrifac): Camera system with integrated artificial intelligence. The system uses boom-mounted RGB cameras to detect weeds in crops.
- Camvio H100 (Harventi Vision): Is an automatic steering system for mechanical weeders and interrow cultivators. The system uses computer vision and advanced artificial intelligence algorithms.
- BRAIN (Cambria): The power of artificial intelligence for optical sorting. By autonomously setting parameters, it identifies the elements more precisely. This results in a purer final product with fewer contaminants.
- Mantis (Augmenta): New generation of passive sensor. It combines an 8-spectrum, 4K-camera system, multiple environmental/light sensors and an advanced AI engine to provide a universal crop health index and apply the calculated fertilizer dosage.
- Beeleap (BBLeap): Uses advanced camera sensors and data analytics to track the individual needs of plants in real time. This means that spray application is adjusted based on the specific needs of each plant, optimising the use of resources.
- Perplant (Perplant): Captures data using cameras mounted on farmers' existing equipment. Using Artificial Intelligence to process HD images in the field enables automated spraying with centimeter precision.
- Blaxtair (Arcure): The system integrates AI embedded camera capable of accurately detecting and locating pedestrians in real time, in any posture in all the most demanding work environments.
- Crop Type Classification Using Satellite Imagery (Digifarm): Crop type classification with satellite imagery. Automatic crop classification contributes to sustainable agriculture practices and enhances food security.
- Improvin' platform (Improvin'): Combines the scalability of remote sensing with the precision of growers' inputs. Using satellite imagery data, AI, Machine Learning, IoT-Technology and trained algorithms it detects and verifies: field boundaries, crop type & rotations, cover crops, biomass, yield prediction, tilling practices.
- PlantAI (Solvi): Translates plant-level drone data into actionable management insights. Visually monitoring of every plant in the field to make timely decisions where needed most. Powered by our advanced machine-learning algorithms.
- CoSpectroCam (AgriWatch): Spectral analysis for the environment. Useful in acquiring hyperspectral and high-spatial data for precision agriculture and RS data calibration. The CSC is an optical coaxial assembly of an RGB Camera and a Spectrometer.

Pros of technology:

- **Time and cost savings.** Real-time data analysis allows you to quickly react and adjust the process of, for example, spraying or fertilizing to the current state and quality, health of weeds on the plantation or in the field,
- **High efficiency and quality of transmitted data:** Real-time data analysis allows for a quick response and adjustment of the action to the momentary, local situation.
- **Real-time operation.**
- **Adaptability and flexibility:** vision systems can be easily reconfigured and adapted to changing work conditions, allowing rapid introduction of new products without costly changes to existing equipment and infrastructure.
- **Safety improving:** In the field of safety, vision systems can compliance with safety procedures by workers preparing solutions for spraying and for spraying vehicles and devices for carrying out plant protection and fertilization treatments, where chemically active and health-hazardous substances are used.
- **Interchangeability of components:** Possibility of interchangeable use in one system of many different types of cameras adapted to the parameters to be analysed.
- **Accuracy:** High precision in object recognition and navigation in complex environments.
- **Versatility:** The ability to detect a variety of parameters, such as fruit maturity or the presence of weeds.

Cons of technology:

- **Variable, depending on the operating conditions, precision of the vision systems,** depending, for example, on the stability of the camera mounts and the stability of the entire machine during its working movements, driving through the plantation, cultivation,
- **Complexity:** Requires advanced data processing and AI algorithms, which adds cost and complexity to the system.
- **Weather sensitivity:** May be less effective in difficult lighting or weather conditions.
- **Data transmission:** problems with correct and fast data transmission and storage due to the often-large amount of data generated by the video system.
- **Sensitivity to dirt:** the need to keep the lens clean for good image quality, particularly important in field conditions.
- **Cost:** the purchase of a complete system and its on-going maintenance can generate large costs, which increase depending on its parameters, and it may be necessary to purchase an additional computer to operate the system and to store the data generated by the system.

Trends regarding technology:

- **Cost reduction:** Innovations are aimed at reducing the costs of components and implementation.
- **Machine Learning:** Improving the functions and functionalities of systems, adapting to variable conditions and non-standard applications, such as recognizing specific patterns.
- **Big data analyses:** the enormous volumes of data generated, which can be analysed to detect hidden trends and relationships. Such analysis allows production processes to be optimised, potential future crop conditions to be predicted and countermeasures to be taken, e.g. at the onset of unfavourable trends in the development of controlled crops.
- **Increasing the efficiency of AI:** Advances in machine learning algorithms and artificial intelligence.

Potential agrifoodTEF services and scope:

- **Signal stability:** To test the integration of vision systems with agricultural robots in real time, assessing the effectiveness of automating operations such as mechanical weed destruction between rows and between plants in the row, spot spraying, seeding or fertilization.
- **Integration with Robotic Systems:** Checking the integration of vision systems with agricultural robots in real time, assessing the efficiency of automation operations such as mechanical weed destruction between rows and between plants in a row, spot spraying, sowing or fertilizing.

- Evaluation of the repeatability of the results of measurements and control of the operation of autonomous equipment.
- Resistance to interference and integration of system elements for specific applications and specific agricultural tools.

Tests:

1. **Object recognition:** Vision tests in the field with different plants and weeds, evaluation of the efficiency and accuracy of recognition.
2. **Lighting Conditions:** Tests under different lighting conditions (day, night, fog), assessment of the impact on image quality.
3. **Integration with AI Algorithms:** Performance evaluation of image processing and artificial intelligence algorithms under real field conditions.

Validation:

- Comparison of recognition results with manual determination.
- Tests of repeatability and stability of results under different conditions.

2. LiDAR Sensors

LiDAR sensors as a combination of different types of sensors. Is a remote sensing method that uses light in the form of a pulsed laser to measure distances (including variable distances) between objects. It emits near-infrared waves that bounce off the nearest object encountered in their path, and the sensor then measures the wave's time of flight and calculates the distance between the Lidar and the detected object.

Examples of the use in commercial solutions:

- Mobile robots

- Bug Vacuum (AgroBot): The robot is an autonomous vacuum robot with a combustion engine for lygus pest control that navigates reactively across the field. A fusion of LiDAR sensors identifies people, obstacles and guidance references.
- Land Care Robot (Directed Machines): Navigation tech is use-case specific and fuses data from one or more of RTK/gps, Vision, LPS. Obstacle detection uses rangefinders (e.g., depth camera, lidar, sonar).
- RoamIO-HCT (Korechi Innovations): The robot automates standard horticultural farming. Using a tablet computer users can set inputs for a path planning algorithm. A LiDAR, 2 SONARs, and a camera that runs artificial intelligence algorithms to detect 30+ different "objects".
- Exobot Land-A3 (WTD4) (Exobotic Technologies & Lambers): is a multipurpose tool carrier to perform different agricultural tasks, is equipped with LIDAR sensors that can detect obstacles in the vicinity of the robot and advanced detection technology to effectively identify and control weeds. This robot can navigate autonomously by its onboard processing and sensors.

- Autonomous kits:

Others: Tools & Data

- SCDI Smart Crop Damage Identification (Agrocom Polska): An objective and efficient system for estimating damage to agricultural crops caused by wildlife, weather and other events. The system utilises low-level photographs (from various types of drones) and collates them with existing LIDAR laser data. The system calculates damaged surfaces automatically.

Pros of technology:

- **Light-independent:** The ability to work in a ground or aerial system. Depending on the need, the device can be mounted on a flying unit either on a tripod or on a vehicle, such as an autonomous vehicle,
- **High efficiency and quality of transmitted data.** Real-time data analysis allows for quick response,
- **Lighting independence:** They perform their function both day and night, without interferences caused by shadows, sunlight glare from the headlights of vehicles from the opposite direction,
- **Data Analysis speed:** The analysis of measurement results in their case is much simpler and faster than in the case of visual images, if, of course, only object detection and not object classification is taken into account,
- **Precision:** highly accurate terrain mapping and obstacle detection. High resolution of acquired data: The current parameters of available scanners, range and angular resolution (100 m, 0.1°) meet the requirements for increasing vehicle autonomy,
- An accurate mapping of the landscape on a plantation or crop allowing the acceptance or verification of previously acquired autonomous vehicle tracks,

Cons of technology:

- **Inability to recognize colours and interpret inscriptions:** This can cause a problem in identifying obstacles, assessing the health of plants,
- **Air humidity impact:** Lasers, especially those with a wavelength of 1550 nm, which provide a more accurate measurement, are more dispersed by moisture in the atmosphere. Therefore, in case of adverse weather conditions, problems with accuracy can be expected and must put up with lower scanning resolution.
- **Possibility of eye damages:** Laser beams, especially those with a wavelength of 905 nm, can damage the lenses of the eyes if they come within the field of vision of the eye,
- **High energy consumption:** Increasing with the wavelength and the number of laser pulses sent, higher for 10550 nm wavelength,
- **Cost:** High cost of Lidar sensors,
- **Weight and complexity:** Lidars sensors can be heavy and complicated to integrate into robotic systems.

Trends regarding technology:

- **Cost reduction:** Innovations are aimed at reducing the costs of components and implementation.
- **Machine Learning:** Improving the functions and functionalities of systems, adapting to variable conditions and non-standard applications, such as recognizing specific patterns.

Potential agrifoodTEF services and scope:

- **Signal stability:** Tests of signal stability transmitted to receivers under various atmospheric, terrain conditions, and operating conditions (dustiness, haze).
- **Integration with autonomous systems:** Verification of the integration of Lidar systems with autonomous agricultural vehicles for their autonomous navigation over the area of fields, crops, plantations.

Tests:

1. **3D Mapping:** Creating 3D terrain maps and comparing them with reference data.
2. **Obstacle detection:** Testing the effectiveness of obstacle detection in the field under different conditions (e.g., different vegetation types, terrain slopes).
3. **Autonomous navigation:** Testing the navigation precision of autonomous robots using LiDAR under real field conditions.

Validation:

- Comparison of 3D maps with geodetic maps.
- Analysis of the correctness of obstacle detection in different scenarios.

3. Multisystems for object recognition and mapping (Mix of different technologies: vision sensors, LiDAR sensors)

Multisystems for object recognition and mapping are a combination of the functionality of two different systems (vision and LiDAR technology) to increase the precision and quality of the data acquired.

Examples of the use in commercial solutions:

- Mobile robots (tool carriers):

- Land-A2 (Exobotic Technologies): Navigation system with dual antenna RTK-gps, LiDAR sensors to detect obstacles in the vicinity of the robot.
- Traxx (Exxact Robotics): Is a robot specialised for narrow vines with navigation system with RTK-gps and LiDAR sensors to detect obstacles. It offers a variety of uses (tillage and spraying).
- Oxin (Smart Machine): Is a fully autonomous multitasking robot for safe, efficient, and sustainable vineyards and orchards. The robots drive pre-planned missions using LiDAR and camera for real time driving adjustments and implement positioning and control. Mission and block information is logged by customers using RTK-gps logging devices to create base line drive paths and to identify in orchard hazards and block boundaries.
- Swarmbot 5 (SwarmFarm): Robot platform for horticulture, orchard and large-scale agriculture applications. Navigation system with 2cm RTK GPS with IMU and wheel odometry. Obstacle detection 3D Lidar and 3D time of flight infrared cameras.
- Herbicide GUSS (GUSS): Robot developed for spraying fruit trees. Use multiple precision weed detection sensors target and spot spray weeds on the orchard floor, which reduces material usage and drift during application. GUSS uses a sophisticated combination of GPS, LiDAR, vehicle sensors.
- mini GUSS (GUSS): Mini GUSS is designed specifically for vineyards and high-density orchards. Uses a combination of GPS, LiDAR, cameras and the latest technology to autonomously roll through the orchards, day or night spraying row after row.
- Amos A3/A4 (Amos Power): Navigation sensors include GPS, LiDAR and stereo vision. Obstacle detection is conducted via stereo vision, LiDAR and radar.
- Burro (Augean Robotics): Computer vision system and AI plus high-precision GPS.
- Prospr (Robotics Plus): Is a robust and autonomous multi-use hybrid vehicle that increases efficiency across a variety of crop tasks. A combination of vision systems (LiDAR + cameras), for intelligent obstacle detection and avoidance.
- Harv B8 (Harvest CROO Robotics): Strawberry harvesting robot. The robot navigates via GPS waypoints with Lidar and camera assistance that also does obstacle detection and collision avoidance.
- Compact S9000 (AVL Motion): The robot harvests fully autonomously by following the bed and detecting the asparagus without touching the bed. Based on image recognition and 12 harvesting modules, the robot is able to identify the location.
- Welaser (Pixelfarming Robotics): The robot uses the guidance solution with GNSS/ RTK positioning.

- UAV:

- EA2021A (EAVision): The drone has a binocular vision system, which can automatically avoid obstacles during operation. Can follow ultra-low terrain and is also well equipped for hilly and mountainous scenes. The drone is equipped with a Lidar sensor, a millimetre-wave radar sensor and an ultrasound radar sensor. It is suitable for safe and secure night operations.

- EA-30X (EAVision): The EA-30X is an all-terrain drone for automatic spraying, suitable for complex terrains and crops. The drone has a binocular vision system and can automatically avoid obstacles during operation.

- **Autonomous kits (tool carriers):**

Tools: Smart Weeders

- Karl (KUHN): GPS system and camera-controlled weeders for maize and sugar beet. Thanks to satellite guidance and multiple sensors (Lidar), it can independently detect changing conditions, implement corrective actions and adjust its operating parameters according to the soil conditions and vegetation stage of the crop.

Pros of technology:

- **High efficiency and quality of transmitted data.** Real-time data analysis allows for quick response,
- **Independence from lighting:** Fulfil their function both day and night, without interferences caused by shadows, sunlight or blinding by the light of oncoming vehicle headlights,
- **Speed of data analysis:** The analysis of measurement results is much simpler and faster in their case than for visual images, if, of course, only object detection and not object classification is taken into account,
- **Adaptability to change:** The multisystem nature of navigation data collection and processing allows devices to respond dynamically to changing environmental conditions,
- **Wide operating ranges:** allows mapping in limited areas not covered by GPS navigation.
- **Exact mapping of a landscape or field:** that allows autonomous vehicles to accept or verify previously obtained driving traces.

Cons of technology:

- **High computing power of the system:** Proper real-time operation of the system requires very high computing power and proper overlapping of point clouds generated from information acquired from cameras and sensors;
- **Device costs:** Obtaining the right depth of image requires the use of a multi-camera system and considerable computing power, which affects the cost of the entire control system.
- **Inaccuracy of the position of the autonomous device:** In the case of inability to determine the exact location of the device in the field, its localization error remains variable, since it is based on the last known position and alignment of the robot. Therefore, in such a case, it is necessary to both determine the position on the map and create a new section of the map for the new terrain,
- **Possibility of intentional interference with the system:** For example, by the military,
- **Air humidity impact:** Lasers, especially those with a wavelength of 1550 nm, which provide a more accurate measurement, are more dispersed by moisture in the atmosphere. Therefore, in case of adverse weather conditions, problems with accuracy can be expected and one has to reconcile with lower scanning resolution,
- **Possibility of eye damages:** Laser beams, especially those with a wavelength of 905 nm, can damage the lenses of the eyes if they come within the field of vision of the eye,
- **Inability to recognize colours and interpret inscriptions:** This can cause problems in identifying obstacles, assessing the health of plants,
- **Weight and complexity:** The combination of several systems leads to significant complexity in their integration with robotic systems and it increases the weight of the equipment (devices and their additional elements) that must be mounted on devices, vehicles that are to be controlled.

Trends regarding technology:

- **Cost reduction:** Innovations are aimed at reducing the costs of components and implementation.
- **Machine Learning:** Improving the functions and functionalities of systems, adapting to variable conditions and non-standard applications, such as recognizing specific patterns.

- **Standardizing data transfer** from different devices.

Potential agrifoodTEF services and scope:

- **Signal stability:** Tests of signal stability transmitted to receivers under various atmospheric, terrain conditions, and operating conditions (dustiness, haze).
- **Integration with Autonomous Systems:** Verification of the integration of Lidar systems with autonomous agricultural vehicles for their autonomous navigation over the area of fields, crops, plantations.

Tests:

1. **3D Mapping:** Creating 3D terrain maps and comparing them with reference data.
2. **Obstacle detection:** Testing the effectiveness of obstacle detection in the field under different conditions (e.g., different vegetation types, terrain slopes).
3. **Autonomous navigation:** Testing the navigation precision of autonomous robots using LiDAR under real field conditions.
4. **Compatibility:** Compatibility tests, the cooperation of systems forming one positioning and guidance system installed on the tested autonomous vehicle.

Validation:

- Comparison of 3D maps with geodetic maps.
- Analysis of the correctness of obstacle detection in different scenarios.
- Analysis of the correctness of determining and maintaining the path for proper passage of an autonomous vehicle based on visual data.

5.3. Function: Assessing environmental conditions

The ongoing monitoring of environmental conditions in areas used for agriculture, cultivated fields, meadows and pastures, vegetable crops, flowers, special plants, shrubs and fruit trees, etc. allows for the implementation of all treatments at the most favourable time and conditions due to often rapidly changing weather and environmental conditions. Continuous monitoring of environmental conditions, including soil, allows for constant updating of resource maps, which, together with yield maps, are used to draw up and update application maps, i.e. digital maps, indispensable for controlling the operation of machinery when performing such operations as fertilization, sowing and crop protection, for example.

General scope of use cases:

- Measurements of soil quality parameters.
- Measurements of atmospheric parameters.
- Monitoring of soil condition, its moisture, temperature.

Agricultural technology it applies:

Sowing, planting, field and crop cultivation, crop harvesting

1. **Soil humidity sensors** (*examples of sensor types and applications*)
Environmental sensors are a broad category, encompassing all sensors capable of monitoring the quantities that characterise weather conditions or the microclimate indoors. Among other things, they are used to detect

physical changes in the environment. An example type of sensor for monitoring soil moisture and other environmental parameters is included.

Examples of the use in commercial solutions:

- Autonomous kits:

Tools: Irrigation

- IDROSAT, IDRONE (IDROBIT): IoT solutions for smart irrigation. The system includes: Irrigation scheduling controlled by weather sensors, Flow control and automatic watering calculation for each irrigation sector.
- FARMSENSE (Farmunited): The measuring station provides you with qualified data on the current soil condition as well as the climate and air conditions, which you can use as a basis for more precise irrigation, sowing, fertilization and plant protection measures.

Others: Tools & Data

- Farm Management Software (AGRIVI): An easy-to-use farm management software designed to support farmers in making precise agronomic decisions based on real-time field insights and simplifying farm administration. Real-time microclimate insights straight from fields.
- FieldView (Climate): The FieldView platform is the central hub of digital farming innovation, providing you the choice to access to a broad and interconnected set of tools- from aerial imagery, to insurance, soil analysis and more.
- SatAgro Platform (SatAgro): A wide range of services based on the use of remote sensing in Poland. Software for farmers. Satellite crop monitoring makes it easy to check the current condition of crops in individual fields and plan agronomic treatments. It allows us to observe the variation of plant condition within each field - from sowing to harvesting.
- AGRONETPRO (Agronetpro): Mobile sensors to create your own weather station - the app will provide all the information you need to make the right decisions (wet leaf sensor, humidity and temperature sensor, soil moisture sensor, rain gauge, disease model, weather stations).
- FarmCloud (Agri Solutions): Farm management systems based on the framework AgriDATA software platform.
- AGRIVI Farm Management Software (Agrivi): Farm management software designed to support farmers in making precise agronomic decisions based on real-time field insights and simplifying farm administration. Real-time microclimate insights straight from fields.
- Agro-weather station and sensors (Weenat): A range of up to 8 connected agro-weather sensors to be installed in the farm and linked AI-based predictive tools (such as prediction of water stress or frost).
- Agro-weather station and sensors (Sencrop): A range of up to 6 connected agro-weather sensors to be installed in the farm and linked AI-based predictive tools (such as prediction of water stress).
- Rolnictwo Precyzyjne Andrzej Przeperski; (Precision Farming Andrzej Przeperski): soil scanning, soil sampling.

Pros of technology:

- **Precision:** The ability to obtain precise data on nutrients, pH, moisture, and other key soil parameters,
- **Fertilizer optimization:** Gaining the ability to adjust fertilizer levels to the specific needs of the soil, resulting in better yields, thereby avoiding over-application of fertilizers and crop protection products, reducing production costs,

- **Personalized maps:** Obtain soil maps showing the current soil diversity in a given field. Based on these maps, crop placement, fertilization and other work can be planned with greater precision.

Cons of technology:

- **System costs:** Quite high costs of purchasing system components.
- **Sampling time:** The sampling time for a single soil sample ranges from a few to several minutes, depending on the size of the plot and its configuration. For large plantation/crop areas and multiple samples, it can take up to several days.

Trends regarding technology:

- **Cost reduction:** Innovation is moving in the direction of reducing component and implementation costs.

Potential agrifoodTEF services and scope:

- **Soil quality:** Soil quality tests to verify other methods used for surface soil quality assessment in cultivated fields,
- **Integration with other applications:** Verify the use of research results in other applications that show the abundance of fields and supervise the operation of cultivation, seeding or fertilization or irrigation machinery.

Tests:

1. **Field Mapping:** Creating field maps for the purpose of conducting soil quality measurements, comparison with reference data.
2. **Sampling and analysis:** Efficiency tests and time of soil sample collection in the field under various conditions (e.g., different types of vegetation, terrain slopes) and their transfer for analysis.
3. **Measurement, evaluations of weather components:** Measurements of selected weather components. (humidity, temperature, cloudiness, etc.) in real field conditions.

Validation:

- Comparison of maps with geodetic maps.
- Analysis of the correctness of sampling and sampling time in different scenarios.

5.4. Functionality: Assessing individual and group characteristics of living animals and environmental conditions in their places of residence and life.

The ongoing control of the environmental conditions in livestock buildings, outbuildings, their associated areas (paddocks) and the areas where the animals are housed allows the farm to be managed in accordance with the principles of animal welfare and broad control along with proper supervision over the herds of owned animals. Optimizing environmental parameters in buildings where animals stay allows to provide them with living conditions at the required level, and controlling their health parameters in turn allows for the detection and diagnosis of diseases and other health problems at the early stages of their occurrence. Ensuring and maintaining proper living conditions for livestock and ongoing adaptation to often rapid weather changes is critical for their proper well-being, which in turn leads to their greater efficiency and productivity, and consequently to obtain healthier and in greater quantity livestock products. Another functionality as it fits into this technology is the control of the location of animals in the paddocks around livestock buildings and in pastures.

Agricultural technology it applies:

Feeding, removal of droppings from livestock buildings, control of environmental conditions in livestock buildings, control of livestock welfare

General scope of use cases:

- Measurements of humidity, temperature, chemical composition of the air,
- Monitoring the health and growth status of animals, their anatomical and physiological parameters,
- Supervision over the amount of consumed feed,
- Supervision over the cleanliness of livestock buildings,
- Control of the location of animals,
- Implementation of the milk collection process (automatic milking),
- Implementation of the egg collection process.

1. Livestock handling tool

Sensors use to livestock handling tool as a combination of different types of sensors and utility technologies. Drones, robots, cameras or sensors that monitor physical activity are devices used by owners to help with pet care. They make it possible to quickly solve problems, make decisions or highlighting patterns of animal behaviour.

Examples of the use in commercial solutions:

- Mobile robots

- Mestrobot RS450 (DeLaval): Manure robot. The scraper robot for slatted floors is equipped with features to help maintain hygiene in the barn.
- Optimat (DeLaval): Robotic Feeding. Automatic feeding systems relieve the burden of all routine tasks, while ensuring regular feeding of fresh feed.
- Astronaut 5 (Lely): Robotic milking. With the Astronaut model, we have reduced the number of high-speed movements, creating an energy-efficient system.
- Discovery 90 S/SW (Lely): Manure robot. The fecal removal robot cleans the barn floor continuously: 24 hours a day, seven days a week. It works at predetermined hours and travels the route you designate without disturbing the cows. It makes the barn a clean, safe and friendly environment.
- JOZ Tech Manure Robots (JOZ Tech): The robot offers a range of manure management robots. They use advanced sensor technology to navigate and clean efficiently, ensuring a high level of hygiene in the barn.
- Vector (Lely): Robotic Feeding. Automatic feeding according to the needs of each group of animals is precision feeding.
- Juno (Lely): Robotic feeding. Increasing the frequency of feed pick-up pays off - pick-up encourages cows to take feed frequently throughout the day and night, which increases feed intake.

- Autonomous kits:**Tools: Livestock management**

- Smart Connected weight scale (Digitanimal): An intelligent weighing scale for cattle, sheep, goats or pigs that, without affecting animal behavior.
- Auto-weighing crush Liberty PM 6000 (Maréchalle Pesage): Weighing crate operating in complete autonomy. Weights recording with numbers of electronic ear tags.
- Weights recording with numbers of electronic ear tags.
- Chronopature (Adventiel): GPS collars for cows. Automatic acquisition of data to track the time spent in pasture by the cows.

- Peek Analytics/ Peek Eleveur (Copeeks): Monitoring system for cows, pigs and poultry. The system relies on a camera and temperature, humidity, carbon dioxide (CO₂) and ammonia (NH₃) sensors, placed in the barn.
- Diagno'PEEK (Copeeks): The Diagno'PEEK offer is made up of mobile equipment backed by a data analysis application. The solution collects ambient data in real-time from multiple sensors (temperature, moisture, ammonia (NH₃), carbon dioxide (CO₂), fine particles, brightness, hydrogen sulfide (H₂S), air speed, anemometer, black globe).
- Peek'ture pasture monitoring system (Copeeks): Camera-controlled Livestock monitoring. The intelligent monitoring of your rangelands and pastures.
- Crodeon Reporter (Crodeon): Real-time monitoring of the atmosphere in livestock building. Reporter is a plug & play IoT sensor device with a reliable wireless internet connection using cellular data.
- AIHerd (AIHerd): The system detects early signs of disease at the very first symptom. Cameras detect unusual behavior, variations in feeding or movement, enabling farmers to intervene quickly to ensure animal welfare and prevent the development of disease.
- Pigxcel (Smart Agritech Solution of Sweden): The solution weighs pigs automatically with the help of camera technology and AI.
- PigInspector (CLK GmbH): Camera-based system with 5 water-resistant cameras and 20 LED lights used to assess ear, tail and skin lesions and tail length in pigs.

Others: Tools & Data

- FarmLife (Media): Monitoring system for dairy and suckler cows. The animals are equipped with activity sensors. The services are: heat detection, calving detection, monitoring of thermal stress, activity, feeding behaviors, health and time spend in pasture.
- Sneezy Protect (Adventiel): Monitoring system for pigs. AI-based sound analysis for early detection of respiratory disease of pigs.
- Soundtalks (Boehringer Ingelheim): Microphone-controlled Livestock monitoring. 24/7 sound data analysed using Artificial Intelligence provides you with a trustworthy and objective way of detecting respiratory problems earlier.
- Serket (Serket-tech): Camera-controlled Livestock monitoring. Using regular security cameras and artificial intelligence to identify health and environmental changes early on.
- Activity meter system (DeLaval): Activity trackers. The smartest way to help ensure breeding success and uphold a healthy herd. Activity data is presented on screen in an easy-to-read, graphical format.
- Porphyrio (Evikon Porphyrio): Smart livestock (poultry) management system using data from the barn, time series analysis, prediction and alerting.
- Digit Animal (Digit Animal): Animal GPS tracker, BLE sensors and analytics on the collected data. Control the fattening of your animals.
- StickNtrack (Sensolus): Multipurpose GPS tracker system and dashboarding. All-in-one tracking solutions.
- INSYLO (INSYLO): The platform simplifies the management of your livestock business and provides tools for real-time management of your farm. Achieve zero waste of feed, reduce expenses and improve animal health.
- Weight-Detect TM (PLF Agritech Europe/ Innotech Vision): Estimate the overall weight taking shape measurements in the image. Contactless weighing system. Provides daily report on total pen weight and average animal weight.
- iDOL 65 camera (Dol sensors): Solution for measuring pig weight with the use of 3D technology. All based of thousands of automated digital imaging weights per day.
- STREMODO (FBN): Recognition of the stress screams of domestic pigs.

- PigInspector (CLK GmbH): Camera-based system with 5 water-resistant cameras and 20 LED lights used to assess ear, tail and skin lesions and tail length in pigs.
- Bleeding Control (CLK GmbH): Exact determination of the amount of blood drained after stunning in pigs.
- ChickenCheck Footpad camera (CLK GmbH): Camera system & AI for automatic detection of footpad dermatitis and lesions in chickens.
- ChickenCheck Hockburn camera (CLK GmbH): Camera system & AI for automatic detection of hock burns in chickens.
- ChickenCheck Catch Damage (CLK GmbH): Camera system & AI for automatic detection of catch damage in chickens.
- Tear staining sensor (WEL2BE): Tear staining sensor for pigs.
- ChickTrack (FarmWorx): Activity level of poultry. ChickTrack - A Quantitative Tracking Tool for Measuring Chicken Activity.
- BroilerZoom (Animoni): Assess body weight of poultry. The broiler weight is the single most important parameter in broiler production and processing.
- Smaxtecclassic Bolus (SmaXtec animal care GmbH): The SmaXtec Classic Bolus SX.2 is a device that continuously measures the inner body temperature, rumination activity, and movement activity of cows. It is placed inside the cow's reticulum, and the data it collects is wirelessly transmitted to smaXtec read-out devices in real-time.
- Smaxtecph Bolus (SmaXtec animal care GmbH): The SmaXtec pH Bolus SX.2 is a device that continuously measures the pH levels, inner body temperature, rumination activity, and movement activity of cows. It is placed inside the cow's reticulum, and the data it collects is wirelessly transmitted to smaXtec read-out devices in real-time.
- Smaxtec (Smaxtec Animal Care): The Smaxtec sensor system is an innovative solution for continuous internal health monitoring of cattle. Users can receive data on temperature (also pH values for the research version), crucial for detecting health issues early.
- Kuhtracking (Mechatronic Austria GmbH): Kuhtracking, or Cow Tracking, is a technology used in livestock farming, particularly in dairy farming, to monitor animal health and manage herds. It involves the use of sensors and electronic devices to collect data on various parameters related to the cows' behavior and health.
- Smartbow (Smartbow GmbH): The system is an advanced dairy cow monitoring technology, a leading animal health company. It uses a proprietary artificial intelligence system called Animal Pattern Recognition IntelLigence (APRIL) to identify and locate animals before they show visible signs of estrus and various health-related behaviors.
- PigVision Mobile Sows (AgroVision Poland): The PigVision Sows program makes it easy to enter data on sows and ear-tagged animals. It allows you to access summaries and up-to-date information at any time, providing excellent support for your daily tasks. Sow data is obtained by entering the sow number manually or by scanning a barcode or QR code on the sow card.
- Heatime/SenseHub (SCR/Allflex): Heatime systems/ SenseHub offer advanced monitoring for dairy cows' health and reproduction, using activity sensors to detect heat and health events, providing data for actionable insights to improve herd management.
- CowControl (Nedap): CowControl provides comprehensive monitoring of cows' health and activity, using accelerometers to analyse behaviour patterns, which helps in detecting heat and health events for better herd management.
- MooMonitor (DairyMaster): Is a collar-based system that monitors the behaviour of dairy cows, alerting farmers to signs of estrus and potential health issues through changes in movement and vocalization patterns.

- **CowScout (GEA Farm Technologies):** CowScout utilizes motion sensors to track the activity and behaviour of dairy cows, providing farmers with data to optimize herd management through heat and health monitoring.
- **DeLaval Body Condition Scoring (BCS) System (DeLaval):** The system employs advanced computer vision and image analysis technology to automatically assess the body condition of cows. This system captures images of the cows and uses algorithms to analyse specific body points that are critical for determining body condition score.
- **LiveStock Planner (Hencol):** The weight of the animals is automatically collected when E-ID tagged animals walk through a weighing station several times a day. The system provides forecasts of when the animals are ready for slaughter and meat- feed analyses.

Pros of technology:

- **Real-time operation:** Ongoing, continuous monitoring and reporting of relevant health parameters of animals, livestock housing, etc. allows to control the health status of animals in real time and react quickly in case of any changes and problems.
- **Multitasking:** A significant part of the indicated devices has the ability control multiple environmental and animal health parameters.
- **Simplicity of assembly and use:** Most of the presented devices and control systems are simple to assemble or install and operate, largely operating unmanned once mounted or installed.

Cons of technology:

- **System costs:** In cases of automatic devices for dedicated work: milking parlors, robots for feeding, waste and manure removal, quite high costs of purchasing system components (devices),
- **Targeted application:** Some of the animal health parameter control systems are systemically oriented only for use to the control of a specific type of animal, such as poultry, pigs, cattle.

Trends regarding technology:

- **Cost reduction:** Innovation is moving in the direction of reducing component and implementation costs.
- **Unification of applications:** Checking the possibility of adding other types of animals to the device's work resources and adding additional functionalities.

Potential agrifoodTEF services and scope:

- **Animal welfare:** Tests to determine the level of animal welfare,
- **Integration with other applications:** check, verify use of test results in other in other animal welfare applications.

Tests:

1. **Measurement, evaluation of environmental components:** Measurements of selected components of the animal's environment (humidity, temperature, etc.) in real conditions of livestock buildings.
2. **Measurement, evaluation of animal welfare control devices:** Adjustment of parameters to different types of animals, their age, etc., evaluation of the possibility of device operation during the stay of animals outside livestock buildings.
3. **Functionality of automatic and autonomous devices:** Measurements of the operating parameters of these devices, adjusting their parameters to specific working conditions and animal requirements or conditions, such as those resulting from the construction of livestock buildings or their additional equipment.

Validation:

- Comparison the data collected with official weather and climate data.
- Analysis data collected in different scenarios.

6. Future steps and conclusions

This Yearly Report serves as a valuable resource for understanding the current landscape and future directions of AI and robotic technologies in agriculture. It highlights the growing importance of digital innovation in shaping sustainable and efficient agricultural practices. The report presents the results of continuous monitoring of the latest available technologies and their use cases, focusing on their usability for testing and experimenting with AI and robotic solutions in the agrifood sectors. Monitoring is done in close cooperation with a network of ecosystem partners, including large technology providers and smaller farms and enterprises.

The aim of the catalogue is to present solutions available in commercially available products or tested by AgrifoodTEF in the context of specific agricultural use cases. The overview shows the ranges of possible applications of various application technologies in machinery and implements used in agricultural treatments and technologies, as well as those used inside farms and livestock buildings. This document will be used internally by consortium members to modify the scope of their services to meet the needs of the rapidly changing market for newly developed products. It serves as a baseline document for organizing information on the technologies, their application in agricultural work, their suppliers, and the possibility of their practical application.

Future Actions and Initiatives

To enhance the catalogue's functionality and ensure its relevance, the consortium members plan to implement several key initiatives. These initiatives will adapt the services offered to prepare for upcoming technological changes and new innovations. The targeted scenarios and initiatives include:

- **Development of an online service with search functionality:** a user-friendly online platform featuring an advanced search engine for the catalogue is planned. This will allow users to efficiently navigate and access the extensive array of information in the catalogue, tailored to their specific needs and queries.
- **Introduction of a technology submission feature:** the platform will include a submission form, enabling both partners at AgrifoodTEF and external entities to contribute information about new technologies. This feature is designed to facilitate the continuous expansion of the catalogue with the latest innovations in agricultural technology.
- **Creation of an automated web crawler:** an automated tool that will regularly scan and extract relevant data from updated databases is planned. This tool will not only keep the catalogue up to date but also identify potential business partners interested in AgrifoodTEF's research and development services. Additionally, the tool will scan networks to identify subjects of interest among SMEs, farmers, and agricultural organizations related to hi-tech solutions.
- **Merge existing and potential customer information:** it is planned to merge anonymous information obtained during service provision or the onboarding phase from Service Requests Descriptions. This includes potential AgrifoodTEF customers who will be surveyed.
- **Map technologies utilized by customers of EDIHs:** a yearly survey will be issued to gather relevant information on technologies used by customers of EDIHs for agricultural solutions. This step is a natural progression since the cooperation between AgrifoodTEF and EDIHs is based on common information exchange and assisting customers in solution development.

To implement these initiatives, AgrifoodTEF members will seek information from EDIH companies on the technologies they are currently using, implementing, or developing. This knowledge will help prepare the technical feasibility of validating these technologies under different conditions and identify opportunities for further collaboration.

AgrifoodTEF, leveraging the wide scientific, training, and organizational capacities of its members, can provide extensive access to state-of-the-art tools, training programs, and interactive demonstrations for EDIH member companies.

Additionally, AgrifoodTEF will promote the exchange of best practices and methodologies between different sectoral networks. The first beneficiaries of activities organized through AgrifoodTEF will be companies cooperating through sectoral links in the EIT-Food and EDIHs networks. AgrifoodTEF will share its collection of best practices, learning experiences, and knowledge-based resources, giving stakeholders access to information on digital technologies. By promoting collaboration, sharing best practices, and providing comprehensive training and support, AgrifoodTEF aims to enhance sustainable and efficient food production across Europe.

In conclusion, while the report does not fully answer questions about forecasts for the development of different technologies, it focuses on showing the widest possible range of technologies currently in use and indicates trends in their further development. Continuous evaluation of these resources will help answer questions about the directions of further development of currently indicated technologies and allow new technologies and their practical applications to be added.

